

CHILDHOOD AUTISM AND PSYCHOLOGICAL FACTORS CAUSING IT**Rakhmonova Aishakhan Oribovna**

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Abstract. *The article provides information about childhood autism, which has become widespread among children in recent years, the causes of its occurrence and psychocorrectional work carried out with children with this diagnosis. There are also urgent recommendations for parents for many years and ideas for adapting children with the autism spectrum into society.*

Key words: *Autism, syndrome, correction, symptoms, behavior, care.*

ДЕТСКИЙ АУТИЗМ И ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ФАКТОРЫ, ВЫЗЫВАЮЩИЕ ЕГО

Аннотация. *В статье представлены сведения о детском аутизме, получившем распространение среди детей в последние годы, причинах его возникновения и психокоррекционной работе, проводимой с детьми с этим диагнозом. Также есть актуальные рекомендации для родителей на многие годы и идеи по адаптации детей с аутистическим спектром в обществе.*

Ключевые слова: *Аутизм, синдром, коррекция, симптомы, поведение, уход.*

Every parent dreams that their child will be born full-fledged, mature and healthy. But life is not always as simple as we think. In recent years, due to global climate change and environmental problems, every 88th child is born with autism. What kind of disease is this?

Autism (also called childhood autism) in English: infantile autism, childhood autism [1], early infantile/childhood autism [1], Kanner syndrome or Kanner autism) [1],

DSM-IV Autistic disorder (autistic disorder) [1] is a disorder caused by a disorder of brain development and characterized by pronounced and pervasive deficits in social interaction and communication, as well as restricted interests and repetitive behaviors. All these signs begin to appear before the age of three [2]. Similar conditions with milder signs and symptoms are called autism spectrum disorders.

The causes of autism are closely related to genes that influence the development of synaptic connections in the brain, but the genetics of the disease are complex, and it is currently unclear which has a greater influence on the development of autism spectrum disorders: . In rare cases, the disease is associated with exposure to substances that cause birth defects. Other proposed causes are controversial, in particular there is no scientific evidence to support the hypothesis linking

autism to childhood vaccinations. According to US data [3], in 2011-2012. officially diagnosed with autism and disorder

2% of schoolchildren are on the autism spectrum, up significantly from 1.2% in 2007. The number of people diagnosed with autism has increased dramatically since the 1980s.

Based on age, autism is divided into the following types:

Early childhood autism – up to 2 years;

Childhood autism – up to 2-11 years;

Adolescent autism is 11-18 years old.

Symptoms of Autism

- Social backwardness;
- Talking to yourself in communication, making various movements with your hands;
- Early onset of general symptoms.
- The child's attentiveness to the mother (laughter, physical movements, vocalizations);
- The child is not in a state of “readiness”, i.e. does not stretch out his arms when trying to pick him up, does not try to kneel down, completely stops sucking;
- Reluctance to play in a team, moodiness when playing with parents and other people, desire to play alone;
- Increased sensitivity to sound, light, as well as whims during games, such as frightening, screaming, flying;
- Decreased ability to speak, up to mutism. Echolalia, i.e. repeating words, repeating phrases heard from parents or constantly repeating words heard in cartoons, this is called Asperger's syndrome;
- Picky eating, lack of appetite, poor sleep;
- Does not obey orders, does not look at things shown, does not pay attention to his name;
- Strict adherence to the established order, i.e. waking up at the same time, keeping things in one place, sorting items by shape, etc.;
- Obvious impairment of the ability to speak, to speak in phrases like adults, to repeat the same words, not to engage in dialogue;
- Not afraid of dangers: not afraid of heights, roads, animals, but afraid of simple objects, for example, a boiling kettle, electric lighter, etc.;
- Repetition of movements, rotation, swaying, repetition of gestures;
- Spontaneous appearance of anger, laughter, panic;
- Paying attention to some unusual situations, for example, memorizing difficult-to-memorize numbers, memorizing the words of songs, writing illegible

Added to the symptoms of adolescent autism are the hormonal changes of the autistic person. The psychiatrist makes a diagnosis based only on symptoms. Many children with autism may not conform to the literature on autism symptoms. In some cases, autistic children may also interact with people, making diagnosis difficult.

According to experts, the birth of a child with autism can be caused by vitamin deficiency during pregnancy, an excess of certain substances in the kidneys, severe stress of the mother in the 3rd month of pregnancy, and closeness of family members due to a genetic condition.

The development of the disease in most cases can be caused by vaccinations given to children without confidence that they are completely healthy. This leads to further development of hidden diseases in the child's brain.

Despite the fact that the Uzbek nation is a children's nation, parents of children with this type of disease try to hide the child's illness from public.

It is a pity that the specialists who are able to properly treat this disease and the educational institutions involved in referring the child are unsatisfactory.

The character of these children is different from oligophrenic children; they cannot go out with such children in a narrow circle.

If, when identifying this disease, parents work together with a defectologist, teacher, psychologist, it will be easier for the child to overcome illness and adapt to society.

It is necessary to engage more and talk to children on the autism spectrum, looking them in the eyes, and try to teach them by making sentences in words rather than letters, leaving them a little freedom in the educational process. Also, treatment of this disease requires both material and spiritual costs and labor on the part of parents.

Constant activities with them create the basis for the discovery of the child's unique abilities.

REFERENCES

1. Американская психиатрическая ассоциация „299.00 Autistic Disorder“, Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders, Fourth Edition, Text Revision (DSM-IV-TR). Washington, DC: American Psychiatric Publishing, 2000 — 70 bet. ISBN 978-0-89042-025-6.
2. Американская психиатрическая ассоциация „Diagnostic criteria for 299.00 Autistic Disorder“, Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders, Fourth Edition, Text

- Revision (DSM-IV-TR). Washington, DC: American Psychiatric Publishing, 2000 — 75 bet. ISBN 978-0-89042-025-6.
3. „CDC and HRSA issue report on changes in prevalence of parent-reported Autism Spectrum Disorder in school-aged children“. Media Advisory. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. 2013-yil 7-oktyabrda asl nusxadan arxivlangan. Qaraldi: 2013-yil 9-oktyabr.
 4. Myers S.M., Johnson C.P., Council on Children with Disabilities. Management of children with autism spectrum disorders(ingl.) // Andoza:НпЗ : journal. — Andoza:НпЗ, 2007. — Andoza:Бсоқр, Andoza:Бсоқр. — Andoza:Бсоқр. — DOI:10.1542/peds.2007-2362. — PMID 17967921.
 5. Howlin P., Goode S., Hutton J., Rutter M. Adult outcome for children with autism(ingl.) // Andoza:НпЗ. — 2004. — Andoza:Бсоқр, Andoza:Бсоқр. — Andoza:Бсоқр. — DOI:10.1111/j.1469-7610.2004.00215.x. — PMID 14982237.
 6. Rajendran G., Mitchell P. Cognitive theories of autism(ingl.) // Andoza:НпЗ. — 2007. — Andoza:Бсоқр, Andoza:Бсоқр. — Andoza:Бсоқр. — DOI:10.1016/j.dr.2007.02.001.
 7. World Health Organization „F84. Pervasive developmental disorders“,. International Statistical Classification of Diseases and Related Health Problems, 10th (International Classification of Diseases, Tenth Revision (ICD-10)), 2006.
 8. Спиваковская А. С. Роль осознаваемых и неосознаваемых переживаний в формировании аутистических установок // Бессознательное / Отв. ред. А. С. Прангишвили, А. Е. Шерозия, Ф. В. Бассин. — Тбилиси, 1978
 9. Filipek P.A., Accardo P.J., Baranek GT et al. The screening and diagnosis of autistic spectrum disorders(ingl.) // Andoza:НпЗ : journal. — 1999. — Andoza:Бсоқр, Andoza:Бсоқр. — Andoza:Бсоқр. — DOI:10.1023/A:1021943802493. This paper represents a consensus of representatives from nine professional and four parent organizations in the U.S.
 10. Oliver Sacks. Andoza:НпЗ: Seven Paradoxical Tales. Andoza:НпЗ, 1995. ISBN 0679437851.
 11. Bodfish J.W., Symons F.J., Parker D.E., Lewis M.H. Varieties of repetitive behavior in autism: comparisons to mental retardation(ingl.) // Andoza:НпЗ : journal. — 2000. — Andoza:Бсоқр, Andoza:Бсоқр. — Andoza:Бсоқр. — DOI:10.1023/A:1005596502855.